

Volume-based incompressible diffusion model for the simulation of silicone oil tamponade and emulsification

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Abstract

Physics-based fluid simulation is generally used in film and animation, industrial production and virtual reality, etc., which has brought tremendous benefits to these areas. Moreover, physics-based fluid simulation also can be used to assist in medical disease diagnosis and treatment because of its fast and realistic advantages. In Pars Plana Vitrectomy combined with silicone oil tamponade for the treatment of Rhegmatogenous Retinal Detachment, there is a lack of quantitative research on silicone oil filling amount and removal time. Therefore, we employ fluid simulation in this paper to visualize the effect of silicone oil emulsification and diffusion in this process. An incompressible number density based divergence-free smooth particle hydrodynamics method is proposed through the number density incompressibility mechanism. Furthermore, we introduce the local equilibrium model, the surface tension model and the elasticity model to simulate miscible diffusion phenomena, interphase surface tension of multiphase fluid, and their interaction with elastic materials. Our method can stably simulate multiphase fluid coupling

under strong surface tension and interphase interaction effects of miscible multiphase fluids. Through the visual simulation of silicone oil tamponade, it can effectively help doctors to estimate the amount of silicone oil and predict the impact of silicone oil emulsification on the prognosis of surgery.

Keywords: Multiphase fluid model, Miscible diffusion, Medical visualization, Computer-aided diagnosis, Silicone oil tamponade

1 Introduction

Medical visualization[1] is widely applied to auxiliary diagnosis, treatment planning and predictive simulation. Especially for the treatment of Rhegmatogenous Retinal Detachment (RRD), which is a common vitreoretinal disease characterized, medical visualization is an important auxiliary tool. Currently, Pars Plana Vitrectomy (PPV) combined with silicone oil tamponade is the main therapy for RRD. Silicone oil is a relatively safe and effective intraocular filler[2]. However, emulsification will occur when silicone oil exists in the eyes for a long time, resulting in various ocular complications[3]. Therefore, considering the filling amount and emulsification of silicone oil can improve the success

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rate of surgery and reduce the occurrence of eye complications.

With the current level of medical visualization, doctors cannot directly observe the internal structure of the eyeball. It is difficult to quantitatively analyze the filling material, and there is a lack of visual recognition of the emulsified state of the silicone oil. The application of physics-based fluid simulation in medical visualization can help predictive simulation of PPV combined with silicone oil tamponade surgery. It is feasible to simulate the intraocular silicone oil filling process. The visualization of the surgical process can assist doctors in judging the filling amount and removal time of silicone oil. In order to improve the success rate of surgery, the reliability of simulation data is necessary. For the multiphase flow scene formed by silicone oil and water, the authenticity and stability of the interphase interaction are the current research difficulties.

At present, the fluid simulation method does not have the ability to accurately simulate the process of PPV combined with silicone oil tamponade. Thus, we propose an incompressible number density based smooth particle hydrodynamics (INDSPH) method. Firstly, the linear relationship between number density compression and pressure is constructed. Secondly, a number density incompressible solver is designed to solve the calculation error caused by the heterogeneous rest density of multiphase flow. We combine the local equilibrium model, the surface tension model, and the elasticity model to realize the diffusion phenomenon and strong surface tension of silicone oil and its interaction with the eye tissue.

2 Related work

2.1 Medical visualization

With the interdisciplinary development of medicine and computing science, the research of medical visualization and computer-aided medical diagnosis have made great progress. Cai et al.[4] used machine learning to regard vascular pixels and non-vascular pixels as binary classification, quickly segmenting retinal vessels from the background. Chen et al.[5] utilized a random forest classifier to segment the retinal nerve

fibre layer through spectral-domain optical coherence tomography to assist in the diagnosis of glaucoma and other diseases. Xu et al.[6] proposed a 3D modelling and visualization scheme for silicone oil tamponade surgery to assist doctors in surgical process planning, but the interphase pressure calculation of this method is not accurate. Meanwhile, they did not consider the diffusion phenomenon of silicone oil emulsification.

2.2 Physics-based fluid simulation

Physics-based fluid simulation methods can be mainly divided into three categories: Eulerian, Lagrangian and hybrid methods[7]. The Smoothed Particle Hydrodynamics (SPH) method, a Lagrangian method, simulates fluid by discretizing fluid into a set of particles[8]. Becker et al.[9] proposed a weakly compressible SPH (WCSPH) method based on Tait equation to approximate incompressible fluid. In order to improve the simulation performance and enhance the incompressibility of fluid, implicit incompressible solvers[10][11][12] were proposed.

PPV combined with silicone oil tamponade involves the interaction between silicone oil and water. It is necessary to consider the physical properties of different fluids in order to simulate miscibility and immiscibility. The diffusion equation[13][14] and volume fraction scheme[15] were proposed to realize miscible effects of multiphase fluids. Ren et al.[16] introduced the drift velocity into the SPH approach and simulated the mixing and unmixing effects caused by the relative motion between phases. However, Ren et al.[16] took the centroid velocity as the velocity of the mixed particles, which could lead to the non-zero velocity field divergence and internal expansion of particles. Helmholtz free energy[17][18] was introduced to capture various mixing and separation processes flexibly. Yan et al.[19] proposed the coupling method of multiphase fluids and solids to simulate the interaction between deformable bodies, granular materials and fluids. Jiang et al.[20] established a divergence-free mixture model for multiphase based on volume-weighted mixture velocity, which ensures mass conservation and improves the accuracy of the

simulation. The use of number density[21] limits the density ratio of multiphase flow that can be handled. Chen et al.[22] presented a particle method based on moving least square reproducing kernel. They used the phase field model to ensure the mass conservation and realize phase evolution of multiphase fluids. Ren et al.[23] used deformation gradient to calculate the compressibility of fluid, and achieved better incompressibility for multiphase fluids.

3 Basis of SPH method

3.1 Governing equations of fluid mechanics

In order to truly simulate the dynamic behaviour of the fluid, a mathematical model is needed to describe the physical phenomena and motion of the fluid. The continuity equation is a partial differential equation describing the transport behaviour of conserved quantities. In classical mechanics, the mass and momentum of the flow field are respectively controlled by the following constraint equations derived from the continuity equation:

$$\frac{D\rho}{Dt} = -\rho(\nabla \cdot \mathbf{v}), \quad (1)$$

where $D(\cdot)/Dt$ denotes material derivative and \mathbf{v} is the fluid velocity, ρ is the density. Eqn.(1) represents the relationship between the change rate of fluid density with time and the divergence of velocity in Lagrangian coordinates.

The momentum conservation of incompressible fluid is described by the Navier-Stokes equation:

$$\rho \frac{D\mathbf{v}}{Dt} = -\nabla p + \mu \nabla^2 \mathbf{v} + \rho \mathbf{g}, \quad (2)$$

where p is the pressure, μ is the dynamic viscosity coefficient, and \mathbf{g} is gravity acceleration. Eqn.(2) describes that the velocity change rate is affected by pressure, viscous force, gravity, and plays an inertial role according to the density.

3.2 SPH discretization

The SPH method discretizes the continuous medium into a set of particles and the discrete

physical field into the sum of macroscopic sampling points, as:

$$A(\mathbf{x}_i) = \sum_j A(\mathbf{x}_j) V_j W(\mathbf{x}_i - \mathbf{x}_j, h), \quad (3)$$

where A is any physical field value, \mathbf{x} is the position coordinate, $V = m/\rho$ is the volume of the particle, m is the mass, W is the smoothing kernel, and h is the support radius. The cubic spline function[12] is generally used as smoothing kernel. Eqn.(3) indicates that any physical field value A of i located at \mathbf{x}_i can be approximately obtained by calculating the weighted sum of the values $A(\mathbf{x}_j)$ of all neighboring particles j within the support radius h centered on i .

The density is substituted into SPH discretization Eqn.(3), as:

$$\rho_i = \sum_j m_j W_{ij}, \quad (4)$$

where W_{ij} is the abbreviation of $W(\mathbf{x}_i - \mathbf{x}_j, h)$. The higher order derivative form of value A can be expressed as:

$$\nabla A_i = \sum_j A_j V_j \nabla W_{ij}, \quad (5)$$

where A_i is the abbreviation of $A(\mathbf{x}_i)$. Eqn.(5) is the application form of the SPH method for obtaining higher-order derivatives of physical field quantities.

3.3 Numerical error of density approximation

When simulating the motion of multiphase fluid with a non-uniform rest density field, the mass of different particles will vary. The discrepancy of mass between adjacent particles causes errors of density approximation according to Eqn.(4), resulting in instability in fluid simulation.

This numerical error issue is illustrated on the left side of Fig.1. It has two types of fluid (phase 1 and 2) with different rest densities 100 and 1000 (kg/m^3), respectively. So the mass of particles (with the same volume) representing each phase (m_1 and m_2) follows $m_2 = 10m_1$. Although in the case where particles are evenly

Figure 1: Schematic illustration of density calculation error.

distributed in space without overlapping (presenting an incompressible state), the density approximated according to Eqn.(4) diverges significantly from the rest density near the interaction boundary of the two-phase fluid, resulting in narrow gaps due to excessive pressure.

To resolve the numerical error issue for uneven rest density field, Solenthaler and Pajarola [21] used a number density scheme [24] to compute an adapted density, where the number density is calculated by:

$$\delta_i = \sum_j W_{ij}, \quad (6)$$

and the density calculated using Eqn.(4) is altered into an adapted density as:

$$\tilde{\rho}_i = m_i \delta_i. \quad (7)$$

When calculating the number density, Eqn.(6) sets the contribution of each neighbour particle j to be the same to avoid the error introduced in Eqn.(4). The adapted density in Eqn.(7) is suitable for the explicit pressure method, but it can not be easily integrated with more efficient implicit pressure solvers like IISPH and DFSPH. As shown on the right side of Fig.1, when the compression occurs, the density compression value at the boundary of phase 2 is much higher than that of phase 1. Since the pressure value is computed from the density in implicit solvers, this can cause a large difference in pressures of neighbouring particles which also leads to instability. This suggests that interaction of high-density ratio multiphase fluids cannot be achieved using adapted density method under the condition of Eqn.(7).

In conclusion, the existing implicit multiphase fluid methods cannot effectively handle the unstable pressure field issue when dealing with intense multiphase fluid interaction. In order to solve this problem, inspired by the DFSPH method[12], we propose an incompressible number density based SPH (INDSPH) algorithm to achieve the stable and efficient interaction effect of high-density ratio fluid. Based on the DFSPH method for single-phase fluid calculation, our method converts the pressure term generated by density compression into the pressure term generated by number density compression. The number density compression of each particle produced by the non-pressure term is offset by the pressure force. Therefore, compared with the traditional DFSPH algorithm, the multiphase fluid interaction can be processed more accurately without additional computational overhead.

4 INDSPH method

Based on the existing implicit incompressible SPH method, we construct a simulation framework for the coupling of silicone oil and water, as shown in Fig.2. Aiming at the numerical calculation error of the traditional SPH simulation method in dealing with non-uniform rest density fluid field, we propose an incompressible number density based SPH model (INDSPH) to ensure the fluid incompressibility, which enhances the accuracy of numerical calculation. The local equilibrium multiphase model[20] is applied to simulate the diffusion and emulsification effect between silicone oil and water. The implicit elastic SPH solver proposed by Peer et al. [25] is also incorporated into our framework and is integrated with our INDSPH method. We further introduce the surface tension model from Akinci et al. [26] (cohesion force and curvature force) into the framework to simulate the surface tension between two phases.

4.1 Modification to SPH discretization

Instead of using density as the traditional SPH method, we use the number density to directly represent the compression state of fluid. Our method avoids the approximate error of the tra-

Figure 2: Incompressible coupling framework for fluid, elastic body and static boundary.

ditional SPH and improves the numerical accuracy of multiphase flow interaction without increasing the spatial and temporal complexity of calculation.

We propose to modify the SPH discretization to use the number density. According to [21], The relationship $1/\delta_i = V_i$ holds, therefore based on Eqn. (3) the SPH discretization can be rewritten as:

$$A_i = \sum_j \frac{A_j}{\delta_j} W_{ij}; \quad (8)$$

and the gradient estimation becomes:

$$\nabla A_i = \sum_j \frac{A_j}{\delta_j} \nabla W_{ij}. \quad (9)$$

4.2 Number density incompressible solver

Similar to the relationship between density compression and pressure in the traditional DFSPH method, a stiffness coefficient κ_i is used to establish the relationship between number density compression state and pressure:

$$\nabla p_i = \kappa_i \nabla \delta_i = \kappa_i \sum_j \nabla W_{ij}. \quad (10)$$

According to the Navier-Stokes equation, the pressure force $\mathbf{F}_i^{p_i}$ exerted by pressure p_i on particle i can be expressed as:

$$\mathbf{F}_i^{p_i} = -\frac{m_i}{\rho_i} \nabla p_i = -\frac{\kappa_i}{\delta_i} \sum_j \nabla W_{ij}. \quad (11)$$

By Newton's second law, the force exerted by pressure p_i on particle j should be exactly the opposite of that on particle i . According to Eqn.(11):

$$\mathbf{F}_j^{p_i} = \frac{\kappa_i}{\delta_i} \nabla W_{ij} \quad (12)$$

The non-pressure force \mathbf{F}_i^{advec} in the Navier-Stokes equation, which is the sum of external forces such as gravity, viscous forces, and surface tension, is used to predict the advection velocity \mathbf{v}_i^{advec} :

$$\mathbf{v}_i^{advec} = \mathbf{v}_i + \Delta t \mathbf{F}_i^{advec} / m_i, \quad (13)$$

where Δt is the length of the time step.

The relationship between the material derivative of number density and velocity can be established as:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{D\delta_i}{Dt} &= -\delta_i \nabla \cdot \mathbf{v}_i = -\nabla \cdot (\delta_i \mathbf{v}_i) + \mathbf{v}_i \cdot \nabla \delta_i \\ &= \sum_j (\mathbf{v}_i - \mathbf{v}_j) \cdot \nabla W_{ij}. \end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

From Eqn.(14), an intermediate number density can be obtained which only considers the effects of the advection velocity induced by the advection force:

$$\delta_i^{advec} = \delta_i - \delta_i \Delta t \nabla \cdot \mathbf{v}_i^{advec}. \quad (15)$$

Algorithm 1 INDFSPH iterative solver

while $avg(\delta/\delta^0) > \eta$
 compute δ_i^{advec} (Eqn.(15))
 compute κ_i (Eqn.(18))
 compute \mathbf{F}_i^p (Eqn.(19))
 update \mathbf{v}_i^{advec} (Eqn.(20))

The pressure is then solved to offset the compression in the intermediate number density so that the fluid remains in an incompressible state. To evaluate the compression state of number density, a rest number density is introduced as:

$$\delta_i^0 = \frac{1}{V_i^0}. \quad (16)$$

Since the velocity change of i induced by pressure p_i can be expressed as $\mathbf{v}_i^{p_i} = \Delta t \mathbf{F}_i^{p_i} / m_i$, the change of number density caused by pressure can be accordingly expressed using Eqn.(14):

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta \delta_i^p &= \Delta t \sum_j \left(\mathbf{v}_i^{p_i} - \mathbf{v}_j^{p_j} \right) \cdot \nabla W_{ij} \\ &= \Delta t^2 \sum_j \left(\frac{\mathbf{F}_i^{p_i}}{m_i} - \frac{\mathbf{F}_j^{p_j}}{m_j} \right) \cdot \nabla W_{ij} \\ &= -\Delta t \frac{\kappa_i}{\delta_i} \left(\underbrace{\frac{\left(\sum_j \nabla W_{ij} \right)^2}{m_i}}_{d_i^{p_i}} + \underbrace{\frac{\sum_j \nabla W_{ij}^2}{m_j}}_{d_j^{p_i}} \right). \end{aligned} \quad (17)$$

In order to make particle i incompressible, the change of number density due to non-pressure and pressure force must fulfill $\Delta \delta_i^p + \delta_i^{advec} = \delta_i^0$. Taking Eqn.(17) in it, we can obtain the description of κ as:

$$\kappa_i = \frac{\delta_i (\delta_i^{advec} - \delta_i^0)}{\Delta t \left(d_i^{p_i} + d_j^{p_i} \right)}. \quad (18)$$

The total pressure force on i , which is the combined force induced by p_i and all of p_j , is then computed as:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{F}_i^p &= \mathbf{F}_i^{p_i} + \sum_j \mathbf{F}_i^{p_j} \\ &= -\frac{\kappa_i}{\delta_i} \sum_j \nabla W_{ij} - \sum_j \frac{\kappa_j}{\delta_j} \nabla W_{ij}. \end{aligned} \quad (19)$$

Then, the velocity change of the particle due to pressure is computed with $\mathbf{v}_i^p = \Delta t \mathbf{F}_i^p / m_i$; and the advection velocity is updated to be used in the next iteration:

$$\mathbf{v}_i^{advec+} = \Delta \mathbf{v}_i^p. \quad (20)$$

The advection velocity will be iteratively updated as illustrated in Algorithm 1, until the global compression state of number density meets the standard (η is smaller than a specific number). η in Algorithm 1 is set as 1e-4 in this paper.

4.3 Boundary condition

To handle the boundary between fluid, rigid objects and elastic objects, we divide particles into

static and dynamic particles. Static particles are particles that do not move at all (i.e. stationary rigid particles), and are denoted as \hat{i} and \hat{j} . Dynamic particles are particles that can be moved by force, including fluid particles, two-way coupled rigid particles, and particles in elastic objects, which are denoted as \tilde{i} and \tilde{j} .

Because static particles cannot be moved by the pressure force, $d_{\hat{i}}^{p_i}$, $d_{\hat{i}}^{p_j}$ and $d_{\hat{i}}^{p_j}$ are zero for all stationary particles \hat{i} . Thus, for static particles \hat{i} , Eqn.(17) is changed to:

$$\Delta \delta_{\hat{i}}^p = -\Delta t \kappa_{\hat{i}} d_{\hat{i}}^{p_i}; \quad (21)$$

and for dynamic particles \tilde{i} , Eqn.(17) is changed to:

$$\Delta \delta_{\tilde{i}}^p = -\Delta t \kappa_{\tilde{i}} \left(d_{\tilde{i}}^{p_i} + d_j^{p_i} \right). \quad (22)$$

5 Experiments

To verify the effectiveness of our method, we first conducted a coupling experiment between two-phase fluid and three elastic objects (see Fig.3). Then we carried out an elastic deformation experiment to simulate how biomechanical characteristics can affect tamponade results (see Fig.5). Finally, we simulated the tamponade and emulsification process of silicone oil in the eye (see Fig.6 and Fig.7). Our simulation algorithm was based on C++ coding, using Eigen as a mathematical calculation tool. For visualization, Blender was used for offline animation rendering. We applied surface reconstruction method proposed by Wang et al.[27] to generate fluid surface. We used a 128 GB memory workstation with two 16-core CPUs and a dominant frequency of 2.30 GHz to simulate all experiments.

5.1 Multiphase fluid and elastic object coupling experiment

In this section, experiments are conducted to verify the performance of the INSPH method in simulating two-phase fluid coupling and the coupling with elastic objects. The experiment is shown in Fig.3, where two fluid phases coloured yellow and blue interact with three elastic objects. The density ratio is $\rho_{red} : \rho_{yellow} : \rho_{purple} : \rho_{blue} : \rho_{green} = 1 : 2 : 3 : 4 : 6$. Because of the different densities of elastic objects,

Figure 3: Coupling experiment between multi-phase fluid and elastic objects. The fluid is displayed in cross section. (a-c): simulation process; (d-f): effects of different methods after reaching the steady state.

they are at different positions when the scene is at rest as Fig.3(d-f) shows.

The first line shows the simulation process, where the fluid blocks fall down and clash with the elastic objects. Fig.3(d) uses the DFSPH method. Fig.3(e) uses the number density method by enforcing the incompressibility of the adapted density. Fig.3(f) uses the INDSPH method proposed in this paper. By comparing the simulation results of the three methods, it can be seen that while exactly a half of the red elastic object should be submerged in the yellow fluid because its density is half of the fluid's density, the red object in DFSPH density incompressible calculation is only submerged by less than a half, due to the error in pressure where the density changes sharply. At the same time, our INDSPH method is more stable in pressure calculation and can ensure the red phase is half submerged. On the interface between the yellow and blue fluid phases, DFSPH produces a gap between phases because of the pressure er-

Figure 4: Comparison of iterations between the number density method and our method.

ror. The phases in the number density method are not fully separated. Using our method, no gap is present between the phases and a clear interface between the two phases is maintained.

Fig.4 shows the comparison of iteration times of the pressure solver per time step between the number density method and our INDSPH method in this scenario. The number of iterations using our method is lower than the number density method most of the time, indicating an improvement in efficiency over the number density method.

This experiment shows the effect of two-phase fluids coupling and fluid-elastic coupling, which proves that our method can effectively simulate the two-phase coupling of silicone oil and water, together with the coupling with elastic eye tissue.

5.2 Elastic Deformation from Tamponade

This experiment demonstrates how silicone oil will affect the distortion of intraocular cavity. As is shown in Fig. 5, Fig. 5(a) is the eye model we reconstructed from the MRI image of a myopic patient, which has the irregular shapes at the bottom. We use different materials with various Young's modulus in Fig. 5(b-d) to examine how elasticity affects the result of silicone oil covering the surface of cavity.

The experimental results show that both the irregularity and elasticity of intraocular cavity can affect the shape of silicone oil existing in the eye. As the key issue in the operation of Pars Plana Vitrectomy combined with silicone oil tamponade is to ensure whether silicone oil can cover the retina tear effectively, the biomechanical characteristics for the patient need to be

Figure 5: Simulation of silicone oil tamponade to the intraocular cavity. Both the irregularity of the eye and biomechanical characteristics affect the result.

Figure 6: Visual simulation of silicone oil injection process.

carefully considered before the operation.

5.3 Silicone oil emulsification experiment

In this experiment, our method is applied to the scene of silicone oil tamponade surgery. Fig.6 shows the silicone oil injection process. Silicone oil is injected through the catheter on the left and water is drained from the eye through the catheter on the right. In addition, we consider the effect of surface tension and set the coefficient of surface tension to 3. After the injection of silicone oil is stopped, we turn on the miscibility diffusion term of the local equilibrium model to simulate the emulsification process of silicone oil. And we can control the emulsification degree of silicone oil by adjusting the diffusion coefficient. Fig.7 shows the simulation results of different degrees of silicone oil emulsification in the intraocular cavity at the same time after surgery. The diffusion coefficient of Fig.7(a) is 0.01, and the emulsification of silicone oil is not apparent. The diffusion coefficient of Fig.7(b) is 0.1, where the silicone oil is seriously emulsified.

This experiment verifies that our method can effectively simulate the silicone oil emulsification process in the intraocular cavity after silicone oil tamponade, which can assist the surgeon in determining the appropriate silicone oil injection amount and postoperative silicone oil removal time.

Figure 7: Visual simulation of silicone oil emulsification process with different diffusion coefficient.

6 Discussion

In order to deal with the instability of the DF-SPH method in multiphase fluid coupling, we propose the INDSPH method based on number density incompressibility. In addition, we introduce a local equilibrium model to simulate the mutual diffusion effect of multiphase fluids. Considering the effect of surface tension, the cohesion force and curvature force are combined to model surface tension. A model for elastic materials is also introduced to simulate the interaction between eye tissue and fluid. The experimental results show that our method can be used to simulate the intraocular silicone oil tamponade and emulsification process effectively. However, there are many factors that affect the emulsification of silicone oil, such as the viscosity, purity and volatility of silicone oil itself, as well as intraocular factors such as intraocular bleeding and excessive eye movement. We will focus on analyzing the silicone oil emulsification considering the actual situation to achieve a more instructive simulation process.

Acknowledgement

This research was funded by: Horizon 2020-Marie Skłodowska-Curie Action-Individual Fellowships (No.895941), National Key Research and Development Program of China (No.2019YFC0605302, No.2020YFB0704501), National Natural Science Foundation of China (No.61873299), Key Research and Development Project of Hainan Province (No.ZDYF2020031).

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